

Impact of Environmental Corporate Social Responsibility on Pro-Environmental Behavior in Hospitality Industry: Mediating Role of Green Mindfulness

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Abstract

Emerging research demonstrates that environmental corporate social responsibility (E-CSR) may significantly influence individuals' Pro-Environmental Behavior (PEB). The primary goal of this research is to bridge the knowledge gap concerning the fundamental mechanisms through which E-CSR affects tourists' PEB. To gain a deeper insight into the interplay between E-CSR and tourists' PEB and to explore the mediating influence of Green Mindfulness (GM), this study investigates their interconnected dynamics. The research employs the Partial Least Squares SEM (PLS-SEM) to evaluate the proposed hypotheses. Gathering input from 446 travellers who have experienced Pakistani hospitality through an informal poll, the study reveals that E-CSR significantly and positively influence the tourists' PEB, with GM partially mediating this relationship. This study is equally beneficial for academicians and practitioners.

Keywords: Employee pro-environmental behaviors, environmental corporate social responsibility, and green mindfulness

1. Introduction

Since the 1970s, businesses have addressed environmental issues comprehensively and promptly (Wolff et al., 2018). To understand the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)' significance, it is imperative to focus on the micro aspect of this phenomenon. Despite the transformation in E-CSR studies from institutional and organizational to the individual level, the role of consumers and other external stakeholders in E-CSR has received limited attention within the marketing community (Zhao et al., 2022). Nevertheless, the mechanisms through which E-CSR influences positive attitudes and behaviors among visitors remain uncertain, thus necessitating a heightened awareness of its influence on various tourist behaviors. The participation of visitors in such activities is one of the most significant benefits of executing an E-CSR approach to promote environmentally responsible behavior. Individuals who embrace pro-environmental behavior (PEB) at a location undertake actions like duplex printing, using stairs over elevators, and maintaining cleanliness. Recent studies have found that E-CSR significantly influences tourist behavior, primarily around the topic (Coulombe, 2023; Maqbool & Nazir, 2023; Chen et al., 2023; De Roeck & Maon, 2018). These areas encompass organizational citizenship behaviors, organizational commitment, task performance, organizational identity, and job engagement. Notably, limited attention has been dedicated to investigating the mediating role of Green Mindfulness (GM) in previous studies (Wu et al., 2022; Su et al., 2018; Bradley et al., 2018; Wong & Kim, 2023). Therefore, the foremost objective of this study is to address existing gaps in the body of knowledge. It commences by investigating how E-CSR affects travellers' PEB. Additionally, it introduces and assesses a model that incorporates GM as a mediator in the linkage between E-CSR and visitors' behavior. Thirdly, there is a growing recognition, particularly from a tourist's perspective, that "acts of the morality of tourists deal with ethical issues of tourists" (Tran, 2023), aiming to bring about behavioral changes. Furthermore, the current research underscores the advantages of Pakistan's CSR initiatives.

1.1. Problem Statement and Research Gap

Despite the significance of employee PEB in mitigating environmental impact, few studies have delved into the underlying reasons driving these behaviors. CSR emerges as a potentially crucial factor in this regard. However, much of the existing research has predominantly centred on the global implications of CSR, such as its role in business sustainability and its environmental effects (Bhuiyan, Rana, Baird, & Munir, 2023; Park & Ghauri, 2015). In doing so, it has often neglected to explore the micro-level influence of CSR, encompassing factors like customer attitudes and behaviors (Fatima & Elbanna, 2023). By testing both the direct effect of E-CSR on consumer PEBs and the indirect mechanisms through which businesses' E-CSR initiatives can promote customer PEBs. However, the existing study intends to address the above-discussed gaps in the field.

One of the most important objectives of this research is to examine and validate these concepts, with a specific focus on understanding the influence of GM in shaping the connection between E-CSR and PEBs. GM is defined as customers' sense of responsibility and awareness when interacting with services and engaging physically with a business.

Moreover, after conducting an extensive review of relevant literature, it became apparent that commendable research has been carried out from diverse perspectives around the globe. This study, however, hones in on the

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context of Pakistani tourism, revealing a scarcity of investigations in this realm, especially from the tourist perspective. Given Pakistan's captivating natural beauty, our research is oriented toward understanding the phenomenon from a customer standpoint. With GM assumed as a mediating factor, this study presents valuable notions into the intricate relationship between E-CSR and PEBs.

1.2. Research Objectives

- To observe how E-CSR affects PEB.
- To examine how Environmental Corporate Social Responsibility (E-CSR) impacts GM.
- To track how GM affects PEB.
- To examine how E-CSR and PEB are related and how GM may act as a mediator.

1.3. Research Questions

- Do E-CSR efforts lead to changes in PEB?
- Does GM have a relationship with E-CSR?
- Does GM Influence PEB?
- Is there a connection between E-CSR and PEB that GM can mediate?

2. Review of the Literature and Development of Hypotheses

2.1. Environmental corporate social responsibility (E-CSR)

Due to governments' increasing issuance of environmental regulations, businesses are progressively embracing E-CSR as a comprehensive strategy to address ecological limitations (Jenkins, 2004). The government and various stakeholders within the tourism sector, including clients, staff, and suppliers, hold expectations for responsible behavior from tourists. Contemporary issues, including diversity, globalization, technological challenges, competitive market and environmental degradation, significantly influence tourism attitudes and behaviors (Kurniawati & Mujiyati, 2023). With a focus on the tripartite bottom line encompassing cost-effective, collective, and environmental performance, the existing study intends to examine how tourists consider E-CSR practices within hospitality organizations. While some deem CSR a serious effort to address societal and environmental concerns positively, others believe it is only a symbolic gesture to please stakeholders or avoid legal complications. Ong et al. (2018) suggest that individuals' valuation of organizational activities varies based on the extent of the organization's E-CSR initiatives. Given the challenge of relying solely on objective metrics, a subjective approach is recommended for assessing E-CSR (Richards et al., 2023). A noteworthy avenue for future research lies in the micro-level approach to E-CSR, which is currently underemphasized in the existing literature (Chatterjee et al., 2023).

A traveler's propensity to come up with and carry out eco-initiatives is correlated favorably with the extent to which their place of employment encourages and exemplifies E-CSR activities (Rehman et al., 2022). In organizations where individuals have acquired and shared environmental insights, day visitors are more inclined to participate in ecological activities, integrating their values with the organization's goals (Wu et al., 2022). In particular, tourists' tendency to engage in environmentally conscious behaviors is influenced by their impressions of local efforts to regulate the environment (Gryshchenko et al., 2022). In addition, behavioral reasoning theory demonstrates that guests are more intended to partake in PEB when they feel supported by hospitality (Elshaer et al., 2022). Moreover, it has been shown that E-CSR practices can yield attitudinal, emotional, and behavioral consequences in the organization (Su et al., 2018; Silva et al., 2023). In socially conscious organizations, visitors who engage in organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) are more inclined to manifest it (Chen et al., 2023; Bradley et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2022).

2.2. Pro-environmental behavior

Lynn (2014) identifies three key PEB components: First component pertains to the altruistic (i.e., prosocial) quality of these actions, enhancing the well-being of individuals and organizations. Second category encompasses discretionary actions taken by employees, such as using reduced lighting or opting for the stairs over the elevator. These choices are primarily at the discretion of the individual. The third aspect entails implementing essential measures to improve an organization's environmental performance and contribute to overall environmental protection (Rehman et al., 2023). Varied criteria have been used in prior research to delineate pro-environmental behaviors within the workplace, which could potentially influence organizational choices and the embrace of environmental objectives or regulations.

Research studies have identified two categories of PEB in tourist destinations: the first involves individual, direct actions such as recycling and energy-related tasks, while the second comprises communal, intermediary actions like engaging in eco-helping behavior and eco-civic activities (Zibarras & Coan, 2015; Daryanto & Song, 2021; Zeng et al., 2023; Ren et al., 2019).

Udall et al. (2020) defined PEB as intentional actions to reduce adverse influence on the built environment and natural world. This study employs this definition. Various individual-level factors have been shown to be significant predictors of tourists' PEB, including personality traits, motivation, environmental values, environmental knowledge, habits and self-efficacy. Contemporary studies have also tackled the difficulties associated with developing and evaluating frameworks that elucidate tourists' PEB within the context of the

hospitality industry. An empirical exploration of the determinants influencing tourists' PEB is lacking, with many studies remaining conceptual (Zhang et al., 2023; Miller et al., 2015; Changxi & Shouming, 2023; Xu et al., 2020; Gao et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2020).

Among all pro-environmental activities, energy conservation and recycling aspirations significantly relate to personal behavioral norms, as stated by Thomas & Sharp (2013). In addition, Hornig et al. (2014) suggest several factors influencing tourists' PEB, including education, environmental infrastructure, management support, training, performance evaluation, and financial incentives. Moreover, Tang et al. (2023) assessed sustainable waste behavior by considering the organizational drivers, individual characteristics, and their interaction. They concluded that attitudes towards the environment, waste reduction, and recycling behaviors are influenced by multiple factors, including disregard for the environment and misperceptions about recyclable waste volumes. This rationale is logical to consider.

H1. Participating in E-CSR is associated with an increase in tourists' PEB.

H2. E-CSR and a GM are favorably correlated.

2.3. Green Mindfulness

Numerous definitions of care exist, ranging from the rigorous, including those rooted in Eastern traditions like Buddhist practices (Wallace and Shapiro, 2006), to moderately extreme perspectives (Brinkerhoff and Jacob, 1999). Some definitions have been developed through continuous engagement with individuals (Langer, 1989). The care concept encompasses cognition, emotions, states of mindfulness, extensive internal harmony, and profoundly remarkable experiences within Eastern philosophical and meaningful contexts. While we focus on facets of care for which validated psychometric instruments are available (such as care scales), our current perspective on care does not necessarily preclude these alternative viewpoints.

Minister et al. (2004) elucidates mindfulness as more about how one processes internal changes. The two-part model incorporates self-regulation attention and intention in experiencing. Self-regulated attention is defined as the ability to guide one's focus and bring it back when it strays into mental elaboration (such as rumination). Intention in experiencing entails assessing and approving whatever feelings, opinions, and emotions arise rather than attempting to control, suppress, or manipulate inner experiences.

Psychologist Ellen Langer (1989) emphasizes that the significance of care heavily hinges on how one manages external stimuli. Importantly, mindful individuals contemplate the unique aspects of a situation before determining their course of action rather than relying solely on rigid instructions drawn from past experiences. Secondly, mindful individuals consistently introduce new and diverse information into their knowledge base. Thirdly, mindful individuals better understand their impact on others, as they can see things from different angles. Individuals who engage in mindful practices are better able to exert control because they can shift their attention from the outcomes to how they are being achieved. Intentional action underscores the core principle of all these definitions (Rosenberg, 2004).

Ecologists have formulated various practices and activities centred on mindfulness or our intrinsic connection with the environment to rekindle our sense of affiliation. These include vision quests, ecological guidance, nature therapy, and mindfulness practices. For instance, Fisher (2002) underscores the significance of "Recollection practices for relearning the supreme human art of valuing, giving back to, and remaining aware of reciprocal relationships with an animate natural world". Common terms used in descriptions of Ecopsychology, such as "observing," "exploring," "discovering," and "appreciating," all rooted in mindful engagement, similarly connote "mindful care." In this manner, we depict green care as a contemplative approach that engages with internal and external dimensions.

H3. PEB is positively associated with GM.

H4: GM mediates the positive association between E-CSR and PEB.

3. Methodology

3.1. Respondents and Data Collection Procedure

This study's main focus is those who have stayed in hotels throughout their travels. These individuals make a suitable target group due to their familiarity with the locations and experience with travel and hotel stays. The cross-sectional survey was conducted in prominent tourist destinations of major cities in Pakistan. In the realm of sampling techniques, non-probability sampling (i.e., convenience sampling method) is employed to get the representative sample. Given the large and unknown population, a sample size comprised 450, as proposed by (Hair et al., 2007). The individuals under investigation were specific customers or consumers. Between August and December 2022, data collection was conducted using a survey method. Researchers distributed 1245 questionnaires among visitors and received 465 responses. Out of 465, 19 questionnaires were excluded as respondents did not fully complete them. Thus, 446 completed surveys were utilized for data analysis.

Table 1

Participants' Demographic Profile (n=446)	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Female	122	27.1
Male	325	72.9
Age (in Years)		
Below 18	13	2.8
19-29	211	44.9
30-39	161	34.3
40-49	47	10
50-60	25	5.3
Above 60	13	2.8
Education		
Intermediate	47	10
Bachelor	104	22.1
Master	117	24.8
M Phil	138	29.3
PhD	65	13.8
Marital status		
Single	204	43.7
Married	259	55.5
Others	4	.8
Monthly Income (in PKR)		
< 50,000	138	29.3
50,000 to 99,999	134	28.5
100,000 to 149,999	107	22.7
150,000 to 199,999	42	8.9
Above 200,000	50	10.6
Occupation		
Student	115	24.4
Self Employed	55	11.7
Office Work	72	13.3
Professional Work	94	20
House Wife	10	2.1
Sale/Service Related	23	4.9
Government Employee	102	21.7
Visit frequency		
Once a Year	302	64.1
Twice a Year	88	18.7
Thrice a Year	40	18.7
Above thrice	41	8.5
Favorite Places		
Hilly Areas	176	37.4
Historical	47	10.00
Beaches	43	9.1
Every Type	166	35.2

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

3.2. Measures

This study adopted the scale of the constructs from previous research. The E-CSR scale (9 items) were borrowed from (Turker, 2009). The PEB Scale (5 items) was formulated of earlier studies (Kim et al., 2013; Robertson and Barling, 2013; Kaiser, Oerke, and Bogner, 2007). The GM scale was developed by amalgamating six items from Amel, Manning, and Scott’s (2009) scale. The five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) was used to rank the items.

Figure 2: Measurement Model

4. Data Analysis and Results

SPSS 24.0 and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was considered to analyze the data. In SPSS 24.0, we assessed the reliability of the measures and explored the relationships among their different components and respondent profiles. PLS-SEM was chosen over more traditional multivariate methods. PLS-SEM tests complex models with non-normal data and small sample sizes (Hair et al., 2017). However, researchers used the two steps to test the model. The first step involved evaluating the measurement model, where we assessed the reliability and validity of constructs. The second step consists in testing the structural model, indicating the significance or insignificance of hypotheses.

4.1. Measurement model

Initially, constructs' reliability was measured via Cronbach alpha and composite reliability (CR) to determine the inter-item consistency. Cronbach’s alpha values and CR values for the latent constructs of E-CSR, GM, and PEB were predominantly above 0.70, as Nunnally and Bernstein (1994) proposed, signifying strong reliability. Similarly, factor loadings and average variance extracted (AVE) were examined to test the constructs’ convergent validity. All items’ loadings adhere to a cutoff of 0.60, indicating that all the items are above the threshold value as suggested by Hair et al. (2016). In addition, the AVE are above the accepted value of 0.50, as Fornell & Larcker (1981) proposed (see Table 2).

Moreover, The heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) technique was adopted to assess discriminant validity. The findings indicate that all construct pair values presented in Table 3 fall within the range of 0.85 to 0.90, consistent with the guidelines of Henseler et al. (2015). Moreover, it is posited that diversity in conceptual interpretations promotes a better understanding of warranted differentiation.

4.2. Structural Model

In the structural model, we have tested the hypotheses to determine the significance of path co-efficient, t-value (>1.64) and p-value (0.05) with the bootstrapping method (5000 subsamples). The results demonstrated that all proposed linkages were found to be statistically significant (see Table 4). In addition, the model’s explanatory power was assessed using coefficient of determination (R²). Every number was determined to be higher than the 0.10 recommended limit (Falk and Miller 1992) as shown in Table 5. We also tested the model’s predictive capability using the predictive relevance test Q². The results demonstrate that all Q² scores satisfy the specified criteria (i.e., Q² > 0) for confirming the model’s predictive utility, as Hair et al. (2014) proposed.

Table 2: Reliability and Validity Assessment

Constructs	Items	Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	CR (rho_a)	CR (rho_c)	AVE
E-CSR	E-CSR 1	0.704	0.874	0.878	0.9	0.501
	E-CSR 2	0.737				
	E-CSR 3	0.717				
	E-CSR 4	0.795				
	E-CSR 5	0.764				
	E-CSR 6	0.674				
	E-CSR 7	0.641				
	E-CSR 8	0.659				
	E-CSR 9	0.663				
GM	GM 1	0.685	0.801	0.802	0.858	0.504
	GM 2	0.786				
	GM 3	0.711				
	GM 4	0.774				
	GM 5	0.641				
	GM 6	0.650				
PEB	PEB 1	0.704	0.756	0.767	0.836	0.505
	PEB 2	0.729				
	PEB 3	0.663				
	PEB 4	0.682				
	PEB 5	0.772				

Table 3: Discriminant Validity- Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	E-CSR	GM	PEB
E-CSR			
GM	0.3775		
PEB	0.5198	0.4743	

Figure 3: Structural Model

Table 4: Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses	Relationship	Path Coefficient	Std. Error	<i>t</i> value	<i>p</i> -Value	Result
H1	E-CSR → PEB	0.341	0.292	6.480	0.000	Supported
H2	E-CSR → GM	0.318	0.316	5.403	0.000	Supported
H3	GM → PEB	0.266	0.305	4.448	0.000	Supported
H4	E-CSR → MO → PEB	0.511	0.093	3.058	0.000	Partial Mediation

Table 5: Assessment of R²

Construct	R-square
GM	0.10121944
PEB	0.244911164

5. Discussion and Implications

The existing study examines the direct effect of E-CSR on PEB and the indirect effect through GM by considering the tourists as the target respondents. E-CSR has an impact on both GM and PEB, as shown by the results. According to the UNWTO (2015), People with higher GM are more likely to participate in PEB, which is critical in advancing environmental sustainability. Though prior studies have highlighted the role of tourists' PEBs in reducing environmental impacts, several factors influence the adoption of PEBs, creating obstacles to the development of sustainable tourism (Scott & Gössling, 2022; Bramwell et al., 2017; Nowacki et al., 2018; Liang-Chih et al., 2022; Ginting & Wahid, 2023). Scholars emphasize the importance of understanding factors that could deter individuals from participating in PEBs (Schubert et al., 2020; Bahja & Hancer, 2021; Wu et al., 2023; Font & Hindley, 2017; Salim et al., 2022). This study reveals that the PEB inhibitory mechanism consists of a coherent set of cognitive tendencies. By incorporating moral duty concepts into the study model, a deeper comprehension of the factors driving PEB development becomes feasible. The findings align with other research indicating a positive relationship between GM and PEB (Steg et al., 2013; Groot & Thgersen, 2018; Soopramanien et al., 202; Gupta & Sharma, 2019; Esfandiar et al., 2023). Visitors genuinely committed to environmental preservation are likelier to engage in PEB. In agreement with Mehmood et al. (2023), this study highlights the significance of discovering and evaluating situationally relevant treatments that can improve the links between moral obligation and PEB. However, the study emphasizes the need to take GM into account when promoting sustainable tourism and suggests directions for further study to improve travelers' PEB. The study found that E-CSR can directly and indirectly enhance PEB among tourists, mainly through the mediating effect of GM. This outcome aligns with prior research showing how E-CSR perceptions influence tourists' PEB in different contexts (Sánchez-Marn et al., 2023; Afridi et al., 2023; Liang-Chih et al., 2022; González-De-la-Rosa et al., 2023; Afsar et al., 2018). This study deepens the connections between E-CSR and PEB that were previously established by Gkorezis and Petridou (2017).

5.1. Implications

The results of this research provide important contributions to the literature on environmental management E-CSR. Firstly, it extends our comprehension of visitors' PEB by uncovering its underlying drivers. The results substantiate the hypotheses by Gkorezis & Petridou (2017) and Afsar et al. (2018), demonstrating that individual attitudes, including GM, contribute to the creation of a holistic, interrelated framework that shapes tourists' perceptions and adoption of PEB. Our study advances the knowledge of environmental sustainability within the hotel industry by emphasizing the influence of distinct personality traits and moral commitments. Travellers' sense of moral responsibility may influence their choice to engage in sustainable behaviors while vacationing. Personal ethical values play a significant role in individuals' environmental behaviors within both domestic and social contexts (Gärling, Fujii, Gärling, & Jakobsson, 2003; Bamberg & Möser, 2007). As a result, finding core characteristics and ethical principles that can drive tourists to act ecologically friendly becomes pivotal. Thirdly, from a pragmatic perspective, the study's implications offer essential insights for public policymakers and tourism managers to enhance sustainability efforts. The findings reveal that moral obligation serves as a substantial factor influencing the effectiveness of PEBs, providing policymakers with a deeper understanding of PEB development. This contributes substantial knowledge about sustainability to decision-makers in public policy and tourism. The study proposes the categorization of visitors based on their interactions with the environment as a strategy to promote sustainable behaviors better.

5.2. Limitations and Future Research Directions

Future research should consider exploring additional factors, such as environmental knowledge and moral obligation, that establish the linkage between E-CSR and PEB. This study is one of the first to investigate and apply the notion of GM within PEB's context. The findings of this study can also be used to develop field investigations comparing perceived and actual PEB. It is critical to recognize that this study depended on cross-sectional data; a more extended study transitioning from on-site to offshore settings could give useful notions.

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